

THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENT'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

The term 'motivation' has been derived from the word 'motive'. Motive may be defined as an inner state of our mind that activates and directs our behaviour. It makes us move to act. It is always internal to us and is externalized via our behaviour. Motivation is one's willingness to exert efforts towards the accomplishment of his / her goal. Let us consider a few important definitions on motivation that will help us understand the meaning of motivation more clearly. Educational psychology has identified two basic classifications of motivation - intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation arises from a desire to learn a topic due to its inherent interests, for self-fulfillment, enjoyment and to achieve a mastery of the subject. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is motivation to perform and succeed for the sake of accomplishing a specific result or outcome. Students who are very grade-oriented are extrinsically motivated, whereas students who seem to truly embrace their work and take a genuine interest in it are intrinsically motivated objectives of the study. There is a both quantitative and qualitative techniques for analysis of data. The descriptive analysis like mean, and Standard Deviation, F-test.and percentage analysis was used for the study. The graphical representation of the Bar Graph. The conclusion is that Motivation of students will play great role in minimizing examination malpractices and go a long way in seeing to the realization of educational goal and the students need to be motivated so that they can do better in their academic pursuit. In motivating students, there is need to use both intrinsic and extrinsic ways of motivation. Both ways of motivation are necessary and none of them is dispensable.

Key Words: Motivation & Academic Performance

Introduction:

Societies all over the world have used education as an instrument for the achievement of their national interests and objectives. Education is an instrument par excellence for effecting national development. It fosters the worth and development of the individual, for the individual sake and for the general development of the society (National Policy on Education, 2004). All these call for functional education for the promotion of a progressive and united country. Therefore, school programs need to be relevant, practical and comprehensive, while interest and ability should determine the individual direction in education. It is only when these 2 factors come together that we can achieve the national objectives.

In order to achieve the goals and objectives of education, the government set up 3 levels of education: primary education, secondary education and tertiary education (National Policy on Education, 2004). For the purpose of this research, the discussion is limited to secondary education. Secondary education is the second level of education in Nigeria. According to National Policy on Education (2004), secondary education is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage.

Motivation Theory:

Is motivation an inherited trait like one of the three temperaments (activity, adaptation, emotionality) or is motivation a characteristic that is influenced by reinforcement and consequences that strengthen some behaviours and weaken others? In other words, is motivation something innate that we are born with and that can be created and strengthened by reinforcers external to the learning task, or is it something interwoven with the learning process itself? The foregoing suggests that there are two types of motivation. The first one refers to the capacity to engage in an activity for its own sake, commonly known as intrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is motivation that is influenced by reinforcers or factors outside the individual psyche. Although literature seems to concentrate on intrinsic motivation to explain student success, it is the author's contention that both should be accorded equal attention. With reference to the South African academic environment, it has become evident through research that students from previously disadvantaged backgrounds fall victim to extrinsic motivational factors in their academic pursuits (see, for example, Ruth, 1996).

Objectives:

Objectives are the main areas where the investigator will be conducting the study work. There are two main objectives conducting Undertaken by the investigator in this study.

General Objective:

To find out the relationship between Motivation and Higher Secondary School Students Academic Performance.

Scope of the Study:

Educational psychology has identified two basic classifications of motivation - intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation arises from a desire to learn a topic due to its inherent interests, for self-fulfillment, enjoyment and to achieve a mastery of the subject. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is motivation to perform and succeed for the sake of accomplishing a specific result or outcome. Students who are very grade-oriented are extrinsically motivated, whereas students who seem to truly embrace their work and take a genuine interest in it are intrinsically motivated objectives of the study.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The investigator delimited to the schools available in Theni district.
- ✓ The study is confined in the private, government and government aided schools of urban and rural areas of Theni district.
- ✓ The sample of 300 students is enrolled.
- ✓ The sampling area are the higher secondary school of in and around of Theni district.

Methodology:

Design of the Study: The researcher has identified a problem to investigate the influence of achievement motivation, home environment and study habits on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Sample of the Study: The sample for the investigation consisted of 300 students studying in ninth and tenth class. The stratified random sampling technique was adopted in two stages. In the first stage the stratification was made on the basis of type of management of school (Government and Private) and medium of instruction (English and Tamil). The sampling unit is school.

Tools Used for the Study: T-test and Anova

Analysis and Interpretation:

H01: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on their gender (male / female) of the selected post graduate mathematics students

Table 1: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on gender

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Male	120	3.04	0.450	239	2.187	0.030	S
Female	120	2.93	0.341				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on their gender (male / female) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.030 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a relationship between cognitive style between the groups based on their gender (male / female) of the selected post graduate mathematics students.

H02: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on their locality (rural / urban) of the selected post graduate mathematics students

Table 2: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on locality

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Rural	164	3.02	.38825	238	5.275	.023	S
Urban	76	2.90	.42280				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on their locality (rural / urban) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.023 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a relationship between cognitive style between the groups based on their locality (rural / urban) of the selected post graduate mathematics students.

H03: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the type of institution (Gov /private) of the selected post graduate mathematics students

Table 3: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on type of institution

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Government	46	3.04	.40232	298	1.148	.285	NS
Private	194	2.97	.40303				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the type of institution (Gov /private) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.285 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no relationship between parents occupation and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

H04: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents education (school / college) of the selected post graduate mathematics students

Table 4: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on parents education

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
School level	150	2.97	.39960	298	.431	.512	NS
College level	90	3.01	.40995				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents education (school / college) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.512 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no relationship between parents education and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

H5: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents occupation (Gov/ private) of the selected post graduate mathematics students.

Table 5: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on parents occupation

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation			
Government sector	19	3.04	.39169	298	.643	.521
Private sector	221	2.98	.40447			
Total	240	2.98	.40302			

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents occupation (Gov/ private) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.521 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no relationship between parents occupation and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

H6: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents income (up to 10,000 / above 10,000) of the selected post graduate mathematics students

Table 6: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on parents income

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Up to 10000	127	3.02	.40046	298	.753	.131	NS
More than 10000	113	2.94	.40358				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the parents income (up to 10,000 / above 10,000) of the selected post graduate mathematics students were the level of significance is at 0.131 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no relationship between parents annual income and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

H7: There will be significant mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the usage of social media (always / often / never)

Table 7: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to level of acceptance towards cognitive style based on usage of social media

Level of acceptance towards cognitive style				Df	T value	P value	Result
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Always	10	3.11	.43032	298	1.288	.195	NS
Often	226	2.98	.40376				
Never	4	2.82	.26536				
Total	240	2.98	.40302				

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between mean score difference in cognitive style between the groups based on the usage of social media (always / often / never) were the level of significance is at 0.195 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no relationship between usage of social media and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

Findings:

- ✓ There is a relationship between cognitive style between the groups based on their gender (male / female) of the selected post graduate mathematics students.
- ✓ There is a relationship between cognitive style between the groups based on their locality (rural / urban) of the selected post graduate mathematics students.
- ✓ There is no relationship between parents occupation and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.
- ✓ There is no relationship between parents education and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.
- ✓ There is no relationship between parents occupation and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.
- ✓ There is no relationship between parents annual income and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.
- ✓ There is no relationship between usage of social media and level of acceptance towards cognitive style.

Suggestions:

The factors respondents feeling pretty competent after working at an activity for a while, satisfied with their performance at this task, enjoying doing the activity very much, thinking that they are pretty good towards the activity given to them, thinking it as a boring activity, pretty skilled towards the activity, importance to them to do well at the task, doing activity with a fun, doing the activity, they were thinking about how much they enjoyed it, describing the activity as very interesting, thinking that they did pretty well towards the activity, compared to other interesting and thinking that they did pretty well towards the activity, compared to other students can be taken for the decision making process of the study. Parents and every family member should be involved in motivation of students. Each family member has a role to play in the motivation of the member, who is a student.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that Motivation of students will play great role in minimizing examination malpractices and go a long way in seeing to the realization of educational goal and the students need to be motivated so that they can do better in their academic pursuit. In motivating students, there is need to use both intrinsic and extrinsic ways of motivation. Both ways of motivation are necessary and none of them is dispensable.

References:

1. Tella, A. (2007). The impact of motivation on student's academic achievement and learning outcomes in mathematics among secondary school students in Nigeria. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 3(2), 149-156.
2. Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of educational psychology*, 82(1), 33.
3. Papastergiou, M. (2009). Digital game-based learning in high school computer science education: Impact on educational effectiveness and student motivation. *Computers & Education*, 52(1), 1-12.
4. Black, A. E., & Deci, E. L. (2000). The effects of instructors' autonomy support and students' autonomous motivation on learning organic chemistry: A self-determination theory perspective. *Science education*, 84(6), 740-756.
5. Zimmerman, B. J., Bandura, A., & Martinez-Pons, M. (1992). Self-motivation for academic attainment: The role of self-efficacy beliefs and personal goal setting. *American educational research journal*, 29(3), 663-676.
6. Coleman, J. S., & Department of Health USA. (1966). *Equality of educational opportunity* (Vol. 2). Washington, DC: US Department of Health, Education, and Welfare.